

Trains of Trauma: Partition as Memory in Marvel's *Ms. Marvel*

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Abstract: *This essay examines the representation of the 1947 Partition of British India in Marvel Studios' Ms. Marvel (2022), situating the series within the frameworks of cultural and material memory studies, trauma theory, and postcolonial thought. While Partition historiography often emphasizes political rupture and demographic violence, Ms. Marvel foregrounds the intimate legacies of displacement through intergenerational storytelling. The essay analyzes how the train station sequence operates as a lieu de mémoire, translating collective trauma into sensory fragments of sound and image. Drawing on Marianne Hirsch's concept of postmemory, Aanchal Malhotra's theorization of material memory, and Cathy Caruth's insights on trauma's belatedness, the essay argues that the show frames Partition as an inherited wound mediated through silences, heirlooms, and fragmented narratives. At the same time, by embedding Partition within the superhero genre, Ms. Marvel reframes catastrophe as a means of survival, transforming memory into resilience. Ultimately, the essay suggests that Ms. Marvel exemplifies how global popular culture can act as a site of remembrance, offering diasporic and transnational audiences a renewed engagement with histories of displacement and belonging.*

Keywords: Partition, Cultural memory, Trauma, Diaspora, Superhero genre

Introduction

The Partition of British India in 1947 remains one of the most cataclysmic events of the twentieth century. In the span of a few months, approximately twelve million people were displaced, and as many as two million perished in the violence caused by the division of the subcontinent into India and Pakistan (Butalia 3). While historians have documented Partition through political and demographic lenses, cultural representations have often focused on its human dimensions, through memories, materialities, and traumas. The Disney+ series *Ms. Marvel* (2022), a product of Marvel Studios' global superhero franchise, offers an unexpected yet engaging encounter with the Partition. Particularly striking is its depiction of the crowded train station, where countless people struggle to board departing trains, embodying the disarray, panic, and rupture of migration. This essay argues that *Ms. Marvel* reframes the Partition not only as a historical event but also as an intergenerational memory that continues to shape diasporic identities. Through its visual rendering of the train scene, the series translates trauma into affective spectacle for global audiences, while representing and reimagining suppressed narratives of South Asian displacement. Employing textual-visual analysis alongside frameworks from trauma studies, memory studies, and postcolonial theory, this essay examines how *Ms. Marvel's* Partition sequence recounts the history of fractured nationhood through migration and loss, situating it within the superhero genre's emphasis on resilience and survivability.

Partition as Cultural Memory

Unlike histories of independence that focus on nation-building, Partition narratives often foreground the trauma of forced migration and the fractured belonging. In *Ms. Marvel*, the train sequence becomes what Pierre Nora terms a *lieu de mémoire*, i.e., a site of memory where the past is symbolically preserved and reactivated. For Kamala Khan, the Pakistani-American protagonist, Partition is not lived history but an inherited trauma passed down through family memory. Kamala's great-grandparents on her mother's side, Aisha and Hasan, lived in a village in pre-independence India. Their daughter Sana, Kamala's grandmother, was lost on the railway platform while trying to board the last train going to the newly formed State of Pakistan. She eventually found his father and escaped the chaos, embedding the memories deeply in the family's lineage. As for Sana's mother, Aisha, in Episode 2, Kamala's father, Yusuf, speculates, "She disappeared that night, just like many others did" (*Ms. Marvel* 00:28:57). Sana's survival underscores both the trauma of displacement and the enduring resilience that has been passed down through generations. Marianne Hirsch's concept of 'postmemory' is crucial here: the later generation experiences the trauma of their predecessors not through direct recall but through mediated images, stories, and silences. According to her, the post-generation "reinforce[s] the living connection between past and present, between the generation of witnesses and survivors and the generation after" (48). Kamala embodies this process, inheriting her grandmother Sana's experience of being separated from her father during Partition and reimagining it through her own diasporic consciousness.

While theories of postmemory highlight how Partition persists through belated and fragmentary transmission, Aanchal Malhotra

foregrounds the material and intimate dimension of memory. Partition exists not only in the political history of nations, but also in the private histories of families, in stories carried in silence, in fragments, in heirlooms. In families affected by the Partition, the topic was often avoided directly, but hinted at in silences, unfinished sentences, and the way objects were guarded. With regards to this silence, concealment, and unspoken histories, Aachal Malhotra observes in *Remnants of a Separation: A History of the Partition through Material Memory* (2017), “For the most part, those who witnessed it have either consigned parts of their memory to old age, or have sheathed it in utter silence, folding skillfully into the crevasses of their minds the painful experiences of displacement, violence and immeasurable loss” (“Introduction”). Kamala’s mother, Muneeba, although not a direct witness to the events, also avoids talking about Partition, embodying these silences and untold or half-told stories. Sana’s fragmented storytelling and the heirloom bangle (belonging to Aisha and passed onto Kamala) reveal that Partition is remembered not as a singular narrative but as scattered, intimate, and material memories. Malhotra notes, “The memory buried within ‘things’ sometimes is greater than what we are able to recollect as the years pass. Memory dilutes, but the object remains unaltered” (“Introduction”). Through the bangle, Kamala finds a trigger that makes her see fragmentary visions of the past. In it, she finds a portal into the time of Partition, thus transforming personal inheritance into historical consciousness. Moreover, Partition in *Ms. Marvel* operates within what Cathy Caruth calls the experience of trauma, an event that resists full representation but resurfaces through fragmented, belated images, i.e., “delayed, uncontrolled repetitive appearance of hallucinations and other intrusive phenomena” (11). The train station sequence does not provide a comprehensive history; instead, it offers sensory fragments of

chaos (shouting, running, clambering aboard trains) that gesture toward the incomprehensibility of trauma. By doing so, *Ms. Marvel* positions Partition not merely as history but as cultural memory, transmitted across generations through affective storytelling.

Visual Analysis of the Train Scene

The train is one of the most enduring symbols of Partition. Trains carried millions of refugees across hastily drawn borders. This grim reality has been powerfully memorialized across diverse cultural productions. Literature and film from Khushwant Singh's *Train to Pakistan* (1956) to Ritwik Ghatak's *Komal Gandhar* (1961) have turned to the train as both a literal and symbolic vehicle of this rupture. *Ms. Marvel* continues this tradition, using the train station as a cinematic site of memory. The mise-en-scène of the sequence is crucial. The camera captures the press of bodies, the cacophony of desperate voices, and the uncertainty of direction, i.e., people rushing simultaneously to leave and to stay. The dim, dust-filled lighting and hurried camera movements evoke instability, while the sound design amplifies chaos through the roar of engines and overlapping shouts. Traumatic memory is often fragmentary, as representational completeness is impossible. In "The Traumatic Paradox: Documentary Films, Historical Fictions, and Cataclysmic Past Events" (1997), Janet Walker observes, the most effective works figure the traumatic past as "meaningful yet ... fragmentary, virtually unspeakable, and striated with fantasy constructions" (809). *Ms. Marvel*'s Partition sequence reflects this fragmentary quality, but it also consciously frames itself as intergenerational memory. Oscar-winning director Sharmeen Obaid-Chinoy directed Episodes 4 ("Seeing Red") and 5 ("Time and Again") of the series. She acknowledges that the platform

scene, as shown in these episodes, was indeed a journey through intergenerational memory lane:

When we were standing on the platform there were close to a thousand extras on set in the scene where we'd gone back into 1947. When Kamala was walking on the platform, listening to these snatches of conversations, there was a moment when all of us on set couldn't believe that we were able to recreate Partition and tell this story to this generation. For that time we were filming her walking through that platform, we really were transported into 1947. Each one of us felt the pain of what those families were going through and it felt like we were bearing witness to history. (Mehrotra)

Her words highlight how the production itself became an act of remembrance, collapsing temporal distance by re-enacting Partition for a new generation of viewers.

Most significantly, the scene dramatizes Sana's childhood separation from her father, Yusuf. As she is lost in the crowd, Kamala travels back in time to witness and ultimately ensure Sana's reunion. This blending of superhero fantasy with historical trauma highlights how memory is never a neutral recording but an act of mediation and reconstruction. The show does not aim for historical accuracy in a documentary sense; rather, it dramatizes the disorientation of displacement through stylized spectacle, allowing audiences, especially diasporic viewers, to feel the urgency of Partition's rupture. By using the train as a symbol of both mobility and immobility, *Ms. Marvel* underscores the paradox of Partition migration: movement promised safety but also entailed vulnerability, loss, and violence. The scene's crowded trains thus

become metaphors for fractured nations, incomplete departures, and unresolved memories.

Diaspora, Identity, and Postcolonial Hybridity

While *Ms. Marvel* reconstructs Partition for a global audience, it does so through a distinctly diasporic lens. Kamala Khan, a Pakistani-American Muslim teenager from Jersey City, embodies what Homi Bhabha terms hybridity: the third space that “breaks down the symmetry and duality of self/other, inside/outside” (Bhabha 116). This hybridity is explicitly voiced in the series when Kamala’s grandmother, Sana, explains, “Even at my age, I’m still trying to figure out who I am. My passport is Pakistani, my roots are in India. And in between all of this, there is a border. There is a border marked with blood and pain. People are claiming their identity based on an idea some old Englishmen had when they were fleeing the country” (*Ms. Marvel* 00:25:20). The line captures both the arbitrariness and the violence of Partition’s border-making, while also reflecting the fractured and hybrid identity Kamala inherits. Her encounter with Partition is thus mediated not through nationalistic histories but through fragmented family memory, reimagined across oceans and decades. On one hand, *Ms. Marvel* recovers silenced narratives by centering Muslim experiences of Partition, which have often been marginalized in dominant Indian historiography. On the other hand, as Ananya Jahanara Kabir argues, Partition memory is always refracted by ‘post-amnesia,’ which is “a symptomatic return to explorations of places lost to the immediate post-1947 and post-1971 generations through a combination of psychological and political imperatives” (26). Taken together, these strands reveal how *Ms. Marvel* both restores marginalized Muslim voices of Partition and frames them through the fractured, belated lens of diasporic memory.

The diasporic lens also enables new forms of connection. For Kamala, learning about Partition is a way of understanding her own fragmented identity, i.e., as an American, Pakistani, Muslim, and superhero. It is also through this process that she gains access to the gendered channels in which the intimate memories of Partition circulate. Urvashi Butalia observes that apart from the history books, the Partition also “exists privately in the stories told and retold inside so many households in India and Pakistan” (4). Partition stories are often told within families, passed down through women’s voices, silences, and everyday memories—“their speech, their silences, the half-said things, the nuances” (Kabir 126). *Ms. Marvel* foregrounds this intergenerational female storytelling, positioning Partition as both a national trauma and a personal inheritance.

Superhero Genre and Resilience

What makes *Ms. Marvel*’s depiction of Partition distinctive is its integration into the superhero genre. Traditionally, Partition literature and film emphasize suffering, loss, and silence, whether in works such as Khushwant Singh’s *Train to Pakistan* (1956), Manto’s short stories, including “Toba Tek Singh” (1955), or Ritwik Ghatak’s cinematic laments in *Komal Gandhar* (1961). *Ms. Marvel*, however, reframes the Partition within a narrative of resilience and empowerment. In the train sequence, Kamala not only witnesses the trauma of Partition but actively participates in ensuring her grandmother’s survival. By using her powers to guide young Sana back to her father, Kamala transforms a memory of loss into a story of survival. This intervention illustrates the potential of the superhero genre to reimagine traumatic histories not solely as victimhood but as endurance and continuity.

At the same time, this narrative raises ethical questions. Does transforming Partition into a site of superhero action risk trivializing its violence? Or does it offer new possibilities for engaging younger audiences with histories often excluded from school curricula? The answer may lie in the dual function of popular culture. In her book, *Prosthetic Memory: The Transformation of American Remembrance in the Age of Mass Culture* (2004), Alison Landsberg conceptualises ‘prosthetic memory’ as a form of memory that “emerges at the interface between a person and a historical narrative about the past, at an experiential site such as a movie theatre or museum” (2). Such memories “originate outside a person’s lived experience and yet are taken on and worn by that person through mass cultural technologies of memory” (19). In other words, mass media can create personal memories of events one did not live through, and at the same time foster empathy and shared social responsibility. *Ms. Marvel* exemplifies this, enabling global audiences, many with no direct connection to South Asia, to engage with Partition memory through visual spectacle. As such, the series not only represents Partition but also redefines how it can be remembered. It frames Partition simultaneously as trauma and resilience, silence and storytelling, fracture and continuity.

Conclusion

Ms. Marvel’s depiction of Partition, particularly its crowded train scene, offers a powerful case study in how popular culture mediates historical trauma. By blending textual-visual strategies with intergenerational memory, the series translates Partition into a form accessible to global audiences while foregrounding the diasporic inheritance of trauma. Through memory studies, we see how the show functions as a *lieu de mémoire*, preserving the Partition as cultural memory. Through postcolonial theory, we

recognize how Kamala Khan's diasporic hybridity refracts this trauma across generations and geographies. And through the superhero genre, we understand how Partition can be reimagined not only as a catastrophe but as resilience. Ultimately, *Ms. Marvel* illustrates that even within the structures of global entertainment; popular culture can serve as an archive of suppressed histories. The crowded trains of Partition, once filled with silence and loss, reemerge as sites of memory, enabling new generations to inherit, question, and reimagine the traumas of the past.

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